

Hoodia gordonii

Bitter ghaap

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Group: Eudicot

Size: Up to 1 meter in height

Distribution:

Hoodia gordonii is widely distributed across in the north-eastern part of the Western Cape, the north and north-western regions of the Northern Cape and southern Namibia. It can tolerate temperatures ranging from $>40^{\circ}\text{C}$ to relatively low (-3°C).

Importance:

Hoodia is a genus of succulent plants that is widely used; traditionally by the San people of southern Africa as an appetite suppressant, thirst quencher and as a cure for, amongst other things, severe abdominal cramps, indigestion, hypertension and diabetes. Although relatively difficult to cultivate, Hoodias are attractive plants and are also used for horticultural purposes.

PromethION Sequencing Report:

Output: 48.35 Gigabases

Approximate N50: 9.5 kilobases

Draft Genome Assembly Statistics:

Assembler used: Hifiasm

Genome Length: 0.55 Gigabases

BUSCO completeness score: 98.6% [Single: 95.5%, Duplicated: 3.1%]

BUSCO database: viridiplantae

Assembly N50: 44 663 kilobases

Contig number: 666

Sample Contributor contact details:

Renée Prins

CenGen (Pty) Ltd

cengen@cengen.co.za